

CONFIDENCE, COMMUNITY, AND A COURSE OF ACTION: TAKEAWAYS FROM TEN YEARS OF DIGITAL POWRR TRAINING

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Abstract – Over the past decade, the Digital POWRR Project has undertaken a journey from research initiative to a trusted source of hands-on, community-centered digital preservation training. Informed by participant feedback and an evolving curriculum—including multi-day institutes and the POWRR Peer Assessment Program—this paper shares ten key takeaways from that journey, highlighting what makes digital preservation instruction effective, human-centered, and worth sustained investment, especially for those working in under-resourced contexts.

Submission Type – Full Paper

Keywords – Training, People Capacity, Collaboration

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

The Digital POWRR (Preserving digital Objects With Restricted Resources) Project has, since 2011, explored the challenges of long-term digital preservation in libraries, archives, and other cultural heritage institutions—particularly those with limited financial and technical resources. Launched as a research initiative funded by the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS), POWRR began by evaluating digital preservation strategies for small and mid-sized institutions. What started as a study swiftly evolved into a broader mission: not just to identify workable solutions, but to actively

support practitioners through hands-on training, capacity-building, and advocacy. Initially based at Northern Illinois University Libraries and now co-led at the University of Arizona, POWRR continues to center the needs of under-resourced organizations, particularly those stewarding materials from historically marginalized communities.

POWRR tackles a critical but often overlooked gap in the digital preservation landscape: the mismatch between the urgency of preserving born-digital content and the lack of resources available to those most responsible for doing so. Digital materials are significantly more vulnerable to loss than their analog counterparts, and vast amounts of at-risk content reside in institutions with the fewest means to protect them. These organizations—often small libraries, archives, and community-based cultural heritage organizations—frequently steward collections documenting historically marginalized communities. Yet they are the least likely to have access to the tools, training, or infrastructure needed to ensure the longevity of their digital materials. Commercial preservation solutions are typically out of reach, and many professional development opportunities inadvertently exclude

these practitioners by charging high registration fees on top of costly travel.

In 2014, the POWRR team published a white paper outlining a “good enough” approach to digital preservation.[1] This pragmatic framework encouraged organizations to take small, concrete steps toward stewardship using free or low-cost tools instead of waiting for the perfect (and often unaffordable) solution. In that same year, the team piloted the first in-person, hands-on workshop using remaining funds from the initial IMLS grant. These initial workshops were originally designed to disseminate the results of our research, but it quickly became clear that they met an overwhelming need for basic training. This experience laid the foundation for what would become the hallmark of the POWRR training model: free, practical instruction delivered in an accessible and community-driven format.

These events have continued to the present day thanks to sustained investment - more than \$1.6 million in grant funding - from the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Institute of Museum and Library Services. Over the past 10 years of this digital preservation training journey, the Digital POWRR Project team has continued to update, revise, and expand its curriculum, reaching more than 1,500 practitioners across a range of events and programs. In response to growing interest and evolving needs, POWRR has developed a dynamic, community-centered approach to digital preservation capacity-building. What began as a single-day workshop model has grown into a suite of accessible formats, including multi-day training institutes and the POWRR Peer Assessment Program, which emphasizes peer mentorship, cohort-based learning, and collaborative evaluation. Each iteration of the curriculum has been shaped by direct participant feedback, ensuring that content remains relevant, approachable, and grounded in real-world needs.

Over the past decade, our work as core team members has revealed the real needs of

practitioners working in digital preservation. In this paper, we reflect on that journey and share ten key takeaways—lessons learned from doing the work, many of which center on building confidence and community within the field.

II. REFLECTIONS ON OUR JOURNEY

Over more than a decade of training events, evaluations, follow-ups, and ongoing conversations with practitioners, we’ve identified a set of consistent themes that explain why the POWRR model has been effective. These takeaways reflect not just what participants have learned, but what they’ve needed, what they’ve carried forward, and what has made lasting change possible. The insights below distill ten years of iterative practice into ten lessons that continue to shape how we approach digital preservation instruction, and how we believe the field can better support its people.

A. *Community Takes Work – But It Endures*

One of the most consistent takeaways from POWRR programming is that investing in community building - especially through face-to-face, cohort-based learning environments - leads to stronger, more sustainable outcomes than isolated or one-off training events. Participants consistently report that the most lasting and valuable aspects of their experience are the relationships they build with peers: people they can turn to for advice, empathy, and shared problem-solving long after the training ends.

This focus on community is not incidental—it is designed into every element of POWRR programming. From group discussions and collaborative exercises to structured peer mentorship and cohort check-ins, the emphasis is on building a sense of belonging within a field that many practitioners find isolating. As one participant shared, “I really appreciated hearing from other folks at different institutions who were grappling with the same problems. It made me feel less alone and more like I was part of something.” Follow-up evaluations have shown that participants who train together are more likely to stay engaged in digital preservation work, feel supported in their professional roles, and return to their institutions with a greater sense of agency.

The evolution of the POWRR model has only deepened this commitment. Multi-day institutes allow for deeper relationship-building than single-day workshops, and the recently completed POWRR Peer Assessment Program explicitly centered on trust, peer accountability, and shared learning. These communities of practice are not just warm and fuzzy add-ons—they are essential support systems for digital preservation success, especially for those working without institutional support or technical colleagues. When people know they're not alone, they're more likely to take action and stick with it.

B. Confidence Comes From Doing

Digital preservation can be intimidating, especially for practitioners without a technical background or formal training. One of the most transformative outcomes we've seen across all iterations of POWRR programming is the way participants' confidence grows through direct, hands-on experience. It's not enough to read about tools or hear lectures on standards; people need the chance to experiment, troubleshoot, and build familiarity and confidence in a low-pressure, supportive environment.

Participants often arrive at events overwhelmed and unsure where to begin. Many describe digital preservation as something they know they *should* be doing, but feel ill-equipped to tackle. Our curriculum is intentionally designed to meet them at this point of uncertainty, guiding them through concrete exercises that build familiarity and demystify tools and workflows. We've come to think of this stage as similar to a toddler learning to eat: it's messy, it's sometimes frustrating, but they are showing up hungry - and the only way to learn is by doing. This approach echoes education pioneer John Dewey's philosophy of experiential learning, which holds that deep understanding emerges through direct experience and reflective action, rather than passive instruction.[2]

Through these guided activities, participants begin to trust their own judgment. They learn not only how to use specific tools, but how to evaluate, select, and combine tools in ways that work for their specific context. Over time, this builds a deeper sense of capacity, not just in technical skills, but in decision-making, planning, and self-advocacy. Follow-up surveys consistently show increased confidence as a key outcome, with many reporting

that they returned to their institutions ready to take action or spearhead local efforts. As one participant put it, "Walking the workflows and getting to play with the tools was absolutely key. I didn't just learn *about* digital preservation—I actually started *doing* it." An external evaluator who attended a POWRR Institute echoed these findings, noting that participants reported the sessions "built confidence" and made them "feel better" and "less intimidated" as information was "broken down in manageable chunks." The Institute's structure—a "balance between lectures and hands-on practice"—was praised for improving comprehension. One attendee captured the transformation succinctly: "A lightbulb went off: I think I know now what to do."

The confidence gained from *doing* aligns with broader instructional approaches across the field. For example, the National Digital Stewardship Residency (NDSR) program embedded early-career professionals in host institutions for immersive, project-based learning experiences. Like POWRR, NDSR demonstrated that real-world, hands-on work, supported by mentorship, can rapidly accelerate both skill development and confidence.

The takeaway is clear: confidence is not a prerequisite - it's a product of the process. Creating space for imperfect practice, peer support, and visible progress can radically shift a practitioner's sense of what is possible.

C. Workflows Over Tools

When practitioners first arrive at POWRR trainings, many are focused on finding the "right" tools. It's an understandable instinct. When you're overwhelmed it may seem logical to start with something concrete and downloadable. But we've learned over the years that while tools are important, what practitioners actually need most is guidance on how those tools fit into a larger, sustainable workflow.

This is why POWRR has always emphasized process over product. Our curriculum is built around helping participants understand how discrete tools can be linked together into step-by-step, achievable workflows that align with their goals, their staffing, and their institutional constraints. The POWRR Tool Grid, developed during our early research phase, and later incorporated into COPTR, the Community Owned digital Preservation Tools Registry - remains

a central learning resource - not because it lists what's available, but because it shows how tools relate to one another and to the digital curation lifecycle.

We've also found that participants respond especially well when we connect digital preservation to the workflows they already know - particularly those used in managing physical collections. Framing digital stewardship in terms of familiar tasks like accessioning, inventorying, or rehousing allows participants to see that they already have relevant skills, and that digital practices don't have to feel so foreign or intimidating.

Ultimately, our goal is to help participants shift from asking "what tool should I use?" to asking "what am I trying to accomplish, and what's the best process to get there?" Tools and systems will come and go, but well-understood workflows, and the ability to adapt them, will serve them for years to come.

D. Feelings Matter

Digital preservation isn't just technical work - it's also emotional work. One of the most consistent themes we've encountered in our training events is the deep sense of overwhelm, isolation, and anxiety that many practitioners carry with them. They worry about doing something wrong, about falling short of imagined standards, or about being the only one at their institution who even *knows* what digital preservation is.

That's why we've built emotional support and encouragement into the core of our instructional model. POWRR instructors don't just teach - they cheerlead, validate, and normalize the messiness of learning something new and intimidating. We openly acknowledge that this work can be daunting; that no one has it all figured out, and that perfection is not the goal. This tone of empathetic realism makes a profound difference. Participants tell us that simply hearing "you're not alone" and "you're doing enough" from someone working in the field can be transformative. This approach echoes other instructional models in the field, such as the Digital Preservation Coalition's *Novice to Know-How* program, which emphasizes approachable, practical learning for beginners.

Data from our evaluations backs this up. One attendee noted that what they valued most wasn't just the workshop content, but "how supported I felt the entire time." Another shared, "It was the first time I didn't feel like I was failing at my job."

Research shows that when people feel psychologically safe - a concept defined by Amy Edmondson as a shared belief that it is safe to take interpersonal risks - they engage more deeply, take more chances, and experience more meaningful learning outcomes.[3] Participants walk away not just with skills, but with renewed energy and determination. As we've learned through this work: building digital preservation capacity isn't only about knowledge transfer. It's also about emotional transformation, helping people move from fear and uncertainty to confidence and purpose.

E. Permission to Begin Is Powerful

One of the most powerful things we can give participants is permission to start small. Digital preservation can feel paralyzing when framed as a massive, all-or-nothing project, especially for those working with limited time, staffing, or institutional support. Through POWRR trainings, we emphasize the value of setting concrete, actionable, and attainable goals, even if they seem modest at first.

Whether it's a one-page policy draft, trying out a single triage tool, or selecting a manageable set of files, these low-barrier entry points help participants build confidence, demonstrate value, and gain momentum. Our curriculum integrates this philosophy through structured goal-setting exercises and the creation of a personalized POWRR Plan, a tool that helps participants define next steps based on their specific organizational context. We also draw on experiences from the consulting and nonprofit sectors, where incremental change and internal advocacy are often more successful than sweeping transformation.

Importantly, these small goals are not just "starter tasks." They are strategic, intentional stepping stones toward sustainable preservation practices. Participants leave our events with a clearer sense of what to do next - not in an abstract sense, but in real, practical terms they can implement right away.

Digital preservation doesn't begin with buying software or hiring consultants. It begins with the

confidence to take the first step - and then the next. As one participant in the Peer Assessment Program shared, "I think POWRR really gave me the knowledge and language to start making changes—before, it was more nebulous and abstract, which doesn't always lead to productive conversations or real outcomes."

F. *It's Not a Black Box After All*

For many practitioners, digital preservation feels like a black box - intimidating, opaque, and full of jargon. One of the most consistent pieces of feedback we receive is that POWRR trainings demystify the field and make participants feel like they finally *understand* what digital preservation is, what it involves, and how they can actually do it.

This clarity isn't just about simplifying complex ideas. It's about delivering content in an approachable, transparent, and human-centered way. We intentionally avoid gatekeeping language, acknowledge the messiness and imperfection of real-world implementation, and provide real examples from institutions that look like the ones our participants come from. Our instructors share not only their successes, but also their struggles and lessons learned. That honesty builds trust and makes participants feel like they belong in the conversation.

We also emphasize that digital preservation is not a rigid checklist or a perfect system, but is rather a process of thoughtful risk management, guided by values, capacity, and institutional mission. When we frame it that way, practitioners stop feeling like they're failing, and start seeing what *is* possible within their constraints.

By pulling back the veil, we empower people to see themselves as digital stewards - not someday, not after a degree or a budget increase, but *now*. That shift in mindset is often what makes the difference between training that's informational and training that leads directly to action. As one participant stated in a recent institute evaluation, the most valuable outcome for them was simply "demystifying digital preservation as a field of practice and showing that I am not alone in the struggle."

G. *Rethinking "Under-Resourced"*

When POWRR was first conceived, its mission focused on helping small and mid-sized institutions with limited budgets and technical infrastructure. But over time, we've seen that the need for this kind of digital preservation training cuts across institutional size, type, and perceived prestige. Application data and participant feedback have made it clear: even in large organizations, digital stewardship is often relegated to a single department or even a single person - often with minimal funding or support.

Through years of reviewing applications, we've come to recognize that being "under-resourced" isn't always about institutional size or prestige—it's deeply contextual. Some participants come from small community archives with no IT support and annual budgets under \$1,000. Others represent Ivy League universities, R1 campuses, or major museums. In these larger organizations, the challenges are often ones of scale, internal silos, and unclear responsibility for digital stewardship. Library-based digital preservation programs may exist, but their scope is typically limited to the institution's central collections - leaving smaller units like research centers, departmental archives, or community-engaged initiatives without access to shared infrastructure. We've seen this reflected across tribal archives, HBCUs, public libraries, and museums alike - diverse institutions facing different constraints but united by an urgent need for support. This has pushed us to expand our own understanding of what "under-resourced" means. It's not just about size or funding levels - it's about support, autonomy, time, training, and visibility. It's also about who is empowered to act, and who is left trying to make a case for digital preservation from the margins.

POWRR's success across such a wide range of institutions is evidence that digital preservation capacity needs to be built everywhere. By focusing on adaptable, context-sensitive training, we've been able to serve diverse participants without assuming a one-size-fits-all approach. Our takeaway? Don't assume the need is only at "small" institutions. Invisibility and underinvestment happen in many forms, and the field needs to be ready to meet people wherever they are.

H. *The Need Hasn't Gone Away - It's Grown*

Ten years into offering hands-on digital preservation training, one thing remains undeniably clear: the demand is still enormous, and is, in fact, growing. We regularly receive around 100 applications for fewer than 30 participant spots for POWRR Institute events, with many applications coming from people who have never had access to structured digital preservation training before. This is consistent with findings from the 2021 NDSA Staffing Survey, which showed that many professionals working in digital preservation roles are doing so without formal training, often as just one of many responsibilities.[4] This overwhelming response directly challenges the notion that the field has “caught up” or that this kind of capacity-building is no longer needed.

There is also a persistent misconception that new graduates are leaving MLIS programs equipped with digital preservation knowledge, or that webinars and online resources are able to fully fill this gap. While these formats absolutely play an important role, they often don't provide the depth, structure, or scaffolded learning environment that many practitioners need, especially those working in isolation or in cross-functional roles. A 2022 program evaluation by the Digital Preservation Outreach and Education Network (DPOE-N) similarly found that many professionals continue to seek fundamental training in digital preservation, highlighting an ongoing gap in workforce preparation despite growing institutional demand. [5]

Additionally, our applicant pool has broadened in recent years to include not just archivists and librarians, but graduate students, IT professionals, and community-based memory workers, all seeking meaningful, practical instruction. This shift underscores both the interdisciplinary nature of digital stewardship and the lack of access to formal training for large segments of the workforce.

The takeaway? We cannot assume the need has passed simply because time has. Training access remains uneven, and many professionals, regardless of role or institution type, are still looking for supportive, skill-building opportunities that meet them where they are.

I. Advocacy Is Still the Hardest Part

Even when practitioners leave POWRR trainings with new knowledge, increased confidence, and a clear action plan, many still return to institutions where digital preservation remains a low priority. This disconnect is not uncommon. As Blumenthal et al. (2020) found in a study of digital preservation professionals, institutional misunderstandings around the purpose and value of digital stewardship frequently result in a lack of long-term vision, unclear roles, and insufficient support for meaningful progress. [6] Again and again, participants tell us that the biggest barrier they face isn't technical - it's internal advocacy: convincing leadership, colleagues, or funders that this work matters, deserves resources, and can't be postponed indefinitely.

This is true even for participants whose job titles explicitly include digital preservation. Being a “digital preservation librarian” or “digital archivist” doesn't guarantee the authority or support needed to build infrastructure, set policy, or purchase storage. For others, digital stewardship is just one small part of a much broader portfolio, and they struggle to carve out time or attention for it at all. We've also seen how the invisible labor of advocacy - writing memos, making the case in meetings, building cross-departmental relationships - takes a significant emotional toll. Participants often leave our events energized, only to feel that momentum stall once they're back in environments that don't understand or value the work.

To support this need, POWRR trainings include explicit instruction in internal advocacy and institutional storytelling, teaching participants how to frame digital preservation in ways that align with organizational values, risk mitigation strategies, and mission-driven goals. We've also found that the cohort model provides an invaluable source of encouragement and strategy-sharing. Just knowing others are navigating the same uphill battles helps practitioners feel less alone - and more equipped to persist.

The takeaway is clear: technical skills are necessary, but not sufficient. Digital preservation success depends just as much on communication, advocacy, and the ability to build buy-in, often from the ground up.

J. The Future is Precarious (But Promising)

POWRR's success over the past decade has made one thing clear: deep, human-centered training works. It builds capacity. It builds confidence. It builds community. But this kind of training is also resource-intensive, and increasingly under threat. Recent moves by the U.S. federal government to eliminate funding for agencies like the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) and the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) jeopardize the very foundation on which community-based programs like POWRR are built.

Unlike webinars or conference presentations, immersive, multi-day training - especially when offered free of charge and with travel support - requires real investment. But it is this very structure that enables participation from those most often excluded from professional development: practitioners at small or rural institutions, BIPOC-led archives, tribal libraries, lone arrangers, and those who have never had the chance to attend training events before.

We know this model works. We've refined it year after year in response to participant feedback. We've watched people walk in feeling uncertain and walk out galvanized to take action. As one participant in the Peer Assessment Program reflected, "I think my involvement in the program has transformed my institution's preservation trajectory. We would not be where we are today without the program... For the first time, I feel like I can actually visualize our path forward." Yet despite its proven impact, programs like POWRR continue to operate in a state of constant precarity - relying on cycles of grant writing, soft money, and the limited capacity of project-based teams to keep going. POWRR is absolutely not alone in this space. Other grassroots training efforts - such as the Community Archiving Workshop from the Association of Moving Image Archivists, the WiLS Curating Community Digital Collections initiative, the Sustainable Heritage Network, and the XFR Collective have also stepped in to fill critical gaps in digital preservation education. These programs share POWRR's bedrock values: community-based learning, real-world skill-building, and accessibility for under-resourced practitioners. And like POWRR, they've faced ongoing challenges related to sustainability, generally relying on limited-term

grants, volunteer labor, or institutional goodwill to survive.

The takeaway here is not just about POWRR - it's about the field. If we want digital preservation to be sustainable, inclusive, and broadly adopted, we must build infrastructure to support the training that makes that possible. This means rethinking funding models, valuing community-based work, and finding ways to resource long-term, hands-on learning as a necessity and not a privilege. The work of digital preservation is a journey that requires ongoing training.

III. CONCLUSION

Over the past decade, the Digital POWRR Project has helped numerous practitioners gain confidence, take action, and build sustainable practices for digital stewardship. But one thing remains clear: this kind of transformative training is difficult to sustain. While demand has grown, consistent support has not. Deep, hands-on instruction is time- and labor-intensive. It requires relationship-building, follow-up, and care. Yet funding remains precarious, and the infrastructure to support this work is fragmented at best.

There are bright spots. The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) continues to provide leadership and high-quality resources to its member institutions, and professional organizations like the Society of American Archivists (SAA) have introduced certificate programs that offer foundational instruction. However, access to these resources often depends on institutional membership or individual financial investment, models that can inadvertently exclude the practitioners who need them most.

POWRR participants regularly express a desire for more peer-based learning environments that are collaborative, supportive, and rooted in shared experience. Many arrive having completed formal coursework and still feel unsure of how to apply it. This reinforces the need for training that is hands-on, community-supported, and responsive to real-world conditions, not just at the beginner level, but across the full continuum of learning. This continued emphasis on core skills is echoed in a 2024 study by Mudle and Cocciolo, who found that cultural heritage professionals most frequently requested training in foundational areas like digital records management

and metadata standards, highlighting an ongoing need for practical, applied instruction in digital preservation.[7]

If we want digital preservation to be sustainable, inclusive, and widely adopted, we must invest in the infrastructure that supports that growth. This means valuing and resourcing not just tools, but the full spectrum of learning opportunities, across formats, skill levels, and professional contexts. A 2017 report from the Institute of Museum and Library Services underscored this need, calling for more accessible and open professional development opportunities in digital preservation. Yet nearly a decade later, many of the gaps identified in that report remain unresolved - particularly for under-resourced institutions. [8]

What might it look like to collectively build this infrastructure? How might funders, professional associations, consortia, and community-based projects work together to create something more inclusive, more scalable, and more sustainable? We invite the field to join us in exploring these questions - and building new pathways forward.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Schumacher, et al., "From theory to action: Good enough digital preservation solutions for under-resourced cultural heritage institutions," *Institute of Museum and Library Services*, Aug. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://huskiecommons.lib.niu.edu/allfaculty-peerpub/1056/>
- [2] J. Dewey. *Experience and Education*. New York: Macmillan, 1938.
- [3] A.C. Edmondson, *The Fearless Organization: Creating Psychological Safety in the Workplace for Learning, Innovation, and Growth*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley, 2018.
- [4] NDSA Staffing Survey Working Group, "2021 Staffing Survey Report." National Digital Stewardship Alliance, Aug. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://osf.io/emwy4/>
- [5] N. Baur. "Digital Preservation Outreach and Education Network Program Evaluation 2020-2022," DPOE-N, 2022.[Online] Available: https://www.dpoe.network/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/dpoen_2020-2022_evaluation.pdf
- [6] K-R. Blumenthal, P. Griesinger, P., J.Y. Kim, S. Peltzman, and V. Steeves, "What's wrong with digital stewardship: Evaluating the organization of digital preservation programs from practitioners' perspectives," *Journal of Contemporary Archival Studies*, vol. 7, no. 1, Article 13, 2020. [Online] Available: <https://elischolar.library.yale.edu/jcas/vol7/iss1/13/>
- [7] K. Mudle and A. Cocciolo, "What needs to be learned by U.S. cultural heritage professionals? Results from the Digital Preservation Outreach and Education Network." *Preservation, Digital Technology & Culture*, Apr. 2024.[online] Available: <https://doi.org/10.1515/pdct-2024-0024>
- [8] M. Gallinger, "Open digital preservation training and professional development opportunities," *Institute of Museum and Library Services*, 2017.[Online] Available: <https://www.ims.gov/publications/open-digital-preservation-training-and-professional-development-opportunities>

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to express sincere gratitude to the Institute of Museum and Library Services and the National Endowment for the Humanities for their generous funding of the Digital POWRR Project. Special recognition goes to Dr. Drew VandeCreek, whose steadfast leadership, vision, and grant-writing expertise have been instrumental in sustaining and expanding POWRR over more than a decade. We also wish to thank our many esteemed colleagues who have served as instructors at POWRR Institutes, workshops, and in the Peer Assessment Program over the past decade, including: Lynne Thomas, Martin Kong, Dorothea Salo, Jay Gattuso, Carol Kussmann, Kyle Henke, Stefan Elnabli, Aisha Haykal, Max Prud'homme, Chelsea Wells, Alexis Braun Marks, Sam Meister, Matt Ransom, Patrick Wallace, Karl-Rainer Blumenthal, Guha Shankar, Bari Talley, Siobhan Hagen, Jeff Hancks, and Meg Miner. We also wish to thank the numerous individuals and organizations who have served in other capacities, such as advisors, evaluators, workshop sponsors, and workshop hosts.

